

Two-phase Path Planning for Fuel-Efficient Safe Navigation

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Abstract—This paper presents a method that combines constraint logic programming with model-based simulation to efficiently generate realistic and COLREG-compliant maritime navigation paths. These paths are generated in two phases: first, an abstract path is derived based on dynamic factors such as the initial position, destination, environmental conditions (e.g., leeway), obstacles, and depth data. Second, the path is implemented in a simulation, and feedback is collected for correction. To reduce the complexity of path planning, we introduce additional constraints in the incremental refinement of path planning, based on the geometric conditions of ships' movement. Based on preliminary experiments, this has reduced the complexity of the path search space—by up to 90%, thereby improving the overall path planning efficiency.

Index Terms—Collision Regulations rules, verification, simulation, optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

When applying Collision Regulations (COLREG) rules in concrete situations, there is a bundle of alternative solutions available. Which one is realizable and optimal in a concrete situation depends on a large number of factors such as the characteristics of the vessel (e.g., mass, length, speed), contextual conditions such as drift, waves, visibility, as well as the correctness of GPS and radar data just to name a few. To make navigation decision support algorithms efficient for human-guided and autonomous vessels, a strategy is needed to reduce the complexity of the process to a practically acceptable set of decision alternatives without substantial loss of control quality.

When searching for the optimal path, for example, with respect to fuel consumption, travel time, or route length, the set of path solutions narrows the more accruing constraints it takes into account. As such, the satisfying solution would be the one that lies at the intersection of the sets of optimal, implementable, and safe path solutions for a given situation. The more concrete details are known about the navigation conditions and the physical characteristics of the vessel, the more precise and realistic scenarios can be inferred.

Consider the navigation situation in Figure 1, with two vessels and one obstacle. Vessel1's initial course over ground (COG) is 90 deg and it reaches "head-on situation" with Vessel2 coming from opposite direction with an initial COG

of 270 deg. According to COLREG, both vessels begin the *head on maneuver* and start steering to starboard. Vessel1 also needs to consider the obstacle (island) in its path and select an *avoidance maneuver* (green solid line) and resume its initial route after passing through the north-western cap of the obstacle island. Since both vessels follow the COLREG rules, the computed reference paths (piecewise linear line segments) are safe. However, in practice, the physical characteristics of the vessels and the prevailing sea conditions can affect the implementation of reference paths, potentially leading to significant deviations. In the case of Vessel1, such a path deviation (represented by a blue curvy line) may result in a grounding of the eastern cape of the island.

Fig. 1. Example of head-on maneuver influenced by physical characteristics of the vessel.

To avoid situations like the one presented above, in this work we plan to answer two research questions:

RQ1. To what extent does the integration of vessel dynamics and environmental factors in navigation models enhance the realism and COLREG compliance of generated paths for improved safety analysis?

RQ2. What complexity bounds should path planning models observe to remain efficiently decidable and practically applicable in real-world navigation tasks?

To answer these questions, we propose an approach that combines constraint logic programming with model-based simulation. In the first phase, a piece-wise linear approximation of the safe path is generated using constraint logic programming. This path is then refined in parallel with solving the implementation constraints. Based on the solution of these constraints, the system provides feedback corrections to the path.

By filtering out infeasible configurations early through analytical geometric conditions and simulation-based validation, the complexity of the path search space can be significantly

reduced. Such a reduction is essential for keeping the computational load within practical bounds, particularly when dealing with high-dimensional, NP-complete decision problems, such as safe and optimal (e.g., with respect to fuel consumption) route planning under COLREG constraints.

To exemplify, we apply the approach to a case study in which the models of a marine offshore surface vessel in Dynamic Positioning (DP) operation are co-simulated in the loop with the path planning approach.

To evaluate the practicality and dependability of the solution's planned paths, CLP can be integrated with model-based (MB) simulations. This combination allows symbolic solutions to be cross-validated with dynamic models that replicate real-world vessel behavior across diverse environmental and operational scenarios. The MB simulation acts as a feedback loop to confirm whether the proposed solutions are both feasible and implementable.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses related work. Section III presents the preliminaries, including the foundations of CLP that underpin our approach. Section IV introduces our proposed 2-PPP method, which consists of two main components: generating piece-wise linear path approximation, and plan refinement for reference path correction. Section V describes the implementation framework. Section VI presents the evaluation results, followed by a discussion of key findings in Section VIII. Finally, Section IX outlines potential directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Boizumault et al. [1] applied Constraint Logic Programming over Finite Domains (CLP(FD)) to solve the timetabling problem. However, their approach does not address geometric aspects involving trigonometric functions with non-finite variable domains, limiting its applicability to navigation and trajectory planning problems.

Bellodi et al. [2] proposed using a binary classifier to reduce the complexity of seat traffic constraints by selectively retaining only the effective constraints. They define collision conditions using two constraints constructed from the complement of crossing and alignment avoidance, which simplifies the collision detection process in constrained environments.

Hu et al. [3] presented a multi-objective optimization framework for trajectory planning of autonomous surface vessels, explicitly incorporating collision avoidance and compliance with COLREG rules. Their approach balances safety and efficiency through optimization of multiple criteria.

Pedersen et al. [4] developed a method and accompanying software toolbox for generating realistic ship encounter scenarios to assess vessels' compliance with COLREG regulations. They provide over twenty benchmark cases designed for evaluating path planning algorithms. Their validation methodology is primarily simulation-based, offering a practical means to assess algorithmic performance in realistic maritime contexts.

The novelty of our approach is that by integrating constraint logic programming with model-based simulation, we can derive safe paths under multiple realistic constraints without

hitting severe complexity barriers for Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships.

III. PRELIMINARIES

Constraint Logic Programming (CLP) [5] is a programming paradigm that integrates two declarative paradigms: constraint solving and logic programming. In CLP, program evaluation is performed through model generation, where program clauses serve a dual purpose: generating the solution search space and imposing constraints to restrict it. Constraint satisfaction is verified automatically by a solver using variable labeling functions, which manage constraint propagation and instantiation strategies to explore feasible solutions within the search space efficiently. Prolog (PROgramming in LOGic) is one declarative language that is used in combination with CLP to explore different solutions that satisfy a given set of constraints. It defines *facts* and *rules* to express relationships and it uses a *backtracking engine* to search for solutions. CLP is often implemented as an extension of Prolog by providing specific *constraint domains* such as bounded integer variables or linear and non-linear constraints [6].

In maritime navigation systems, particularly for autonomous vessels, constraints encompass both high-level rules and low-level dynamic factors. These include general parameters such as waypoints, speed limits, and regulatory compliance, as well as vessel-specific characteristics like turning radius, propulsion capabilities, and response time. This layered constraint structure supports modular reasoning and enables formal treatment of navigation decision processes.

IV. TWO-PHASE PATH PLANNING (2-PPP) IN A NUTSHELL

In our context, navigation decisions and conditions are modeled as a constraint system defined over a stratified set of navigation-related data [7]. This ranges from generic path parameters such as speed limits and waypoints to more detailed vessel dynamic parameters including turning radius and thruster capabilities.

A. Solution architecture

The 2-PPP architecture is composed of a Constraint Logic Programming-based Verification Tool (CVT) and a Vessel Simulation Framework (VSF) as shown in Figure 6. By solving safety constraints in conformity with COLREG rules, CVT provides the reference routes of vessels in multi-ship encounter situations. The simulation framework applies the characteristics of the vessel dynamics in the refined simulation and returns the corrections of the reference route together with the operation data of the vessel such as cumulative fuel consumption, thruster power profiles, etc.

CVT functional architecture consists of three core components: Explorer, Solver and Middleware. **Explorer** constructs and explores the combinations of parameter domains that occur in the safety constraints and navigation rules. The instantiated parameter vectors are provided as input to the **Solver**, which uses them for value propagation and grounding of ungrounded constraints. The path planning solutions of

Fig. 2. Overview of the approach

vessels in the form of grounded path constraints are derived simultaneously for each vessel participating in the situation at each time step of the model time. The solution of a time step is transferred via middleware to the simulation framework for refinement and correction (if it turns out to be necessary). The **Middleware** interfaces other two CVT components and mediates data exchange with the VSF. VSF allows to run multiple independent **Vessel simulators** in a distributed manner, each having its own physical characteristics and own simulation environment. The **Controller** module handles the initialization of the vessel simulations with vessel characteristics and initial conditions. Then, each vessel receives from CVT the waypoint coordinates for the next path segment, and it returns, whenever queried, the current vessel position and the cumulative fuel consumption by taking into account also leeway parameters.

To this extent, VSF allows us to check whether the reference paths can actually be followed by the vessel, considering how it handles in practice. To keep things simple and focus on maneuverability, we assume open sea conditions meaning the water is deep enough for the vessel's draft. With that in place, the main factor affecting any needed changes to the planned route is the vessel's turning radius at its normal speed. VSF helps us simulate this behavior and make sure the path is not just theoretically valid, but also feasible in real-life situations.

The result of path actuation at given time step emulated in VSF is returned to the **Solver** as the vessel's actual position, heading and cumulative path cost function and used as instantiations of dynamic parameters for planning in the next time step. Simultaneously to the constraint solving that results in generation of symbolic states of the navigation situation, the **Solver** checks satisfiability of constraints that specify the properties to be verified, e.g., close counter situation between vessels, vessel grounding, or live-lock like behavior.

B. Detailed planning approach

Our path planning approach has two phases: first *piece-wise linear approximation path*, as serializing geographical waypoints, of the safe path is generated using CLP. Then, this path is refined into an *actual path* possibly close to waypoints related to course changes by taking into account vessel characteristics and sea conditions. This actuated path is then used to provide feedback corrections to CVT.

The implementable actual paths refine the linear path segments using a differentiable curve that satisfies the Lipschitz condition [8] meaning that the rate of change of the course is

bounded, preventing sharp turns or discontinuities. However, this refinement may cause the actual path to deviate from the original segments of the linear path. As a result, the original path must be corrected based on the optimized path and its safety re-verified at discrete waypoints where the deviation exceeds an acceptable modeling precision threshold. This ensures that the actual path remains both optimal and safe for real-world execution.

C. Generating Piece-Wise Linear Path Approximation

Figure 3 illustrates that at each time step t_i from 0 to model time horizon T_H , the algorithm iterates over all ships present in the situation model area, called the *canvas*. Each ship, referred to as the *situation evaluating vessel*, and denoted as id_i examines all the other *target ships*, denoted as id_j , involved in a maritime encounter defined by COLREG. For every ship pair $\{id_i, id_j\}$, a series of conditional checks is performed to determine appropriate navigational actions.

Fig. 3. CQS Detection and Avoidance System: Flow Diagram with CLP Clause Block Steps.

The route planning loop at each model time step begins with **Check 1**, which detects if the property to be verified, e.g., a *Close Quarter Situation* (CQS) [9], a spatial condition indicating that two vessels are reaching too close proximity situation and requires immediate navigational attention. Unlike a simple risk of collision, which predicts potential impact based on paths, a CQS emphasizes real-time situational awareness and operational urgency. If a CQS is detected, the current parameters (position, heading, speed, etc.) are logged

(**Step 11**) as witness samples for further safety analysis using situation animation, and the process is stopped.

If no CQS is found, the system proceeds to **Check 2** to evaluate whether a CQS threat (predefined safety envelope as polygon) exists specifically between any vessel id_i and some target vessel id_j . This role assignment is purely functional, as all ships are treated symmetrically and alternate roles during the evaluation process.

Upon detecting a CQS threat, the system instantiates the navigation constraints of COLREG-compliant avoidance maneuver with parameter values set by Explorer (**Step 3**), followed by **Check 4** to verify whether this maneuver encounters any obstacles. If obstacles are present, an alternative optimal avoidance path is computed and integrated into the navigation plan (**Step 5**), after which the system loops back to reassess threats (**Check 2**). If no obstacles are encountered, or if no CQS threat was initially detected, the system advances to **Check 6** to determine if any avoidance maneuver—either for CQS or obstacles—is currently active.

If an avoidance maneuver is underway, **Check 7** evaluates whether the vessel has reached a designated waypoint from which it can safely return to its original planned path. If the waypoint is reached, the vessel turns back to its initial course (**Step 9**); otherwise, the maneuver continues as planned (**Step 8**). Both continuation and return scenarios culminate in **Step 10**, where the system executes the final navigational decision for the evaluating vessel at the current time step.

To summarize, each vessel independently executes its decision-making process based on these local, pairwise assessments, reflecting the decentralized nature of real-world navigation where officers rely on immediate situational perception to make timely collision avoidance decisions.

D. Plan Refinement for Reference Path Correction

The VSF introduces additional parameters and constraints that concretize vessel dynamics, including power, speed, turning radius, and fuel consumption taking into account the speed through water, and also the environment conditions (leeway causes). The vessel’s position and estimated fuel consumption, are then fed back to the Solver and used for the route planning in the next time step. This iterative feedback loop enables continuous refinement of the reference paths, ensuring that planned paths remain feasible and efficient under realistic dynamic conditions.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation is structured around two main components: the CVT and the simulation framework. The verification framework uses `SWI-PROLOG` together with the constraint logic programming library `CLP(FD)` to encode COLREGs and dynamic constraints as solvable logic rules. These logical rules are formulated using Horn clauses in first-order logic, allowing the system to infer navigational situations from vessel states and spatial relationships. For example, vessel dynamics are represented in Prolog as facts such as `ship0/7` and `leeway/4` displayed in Listing 1, which encode the vessel’s current state

including position, course over ground, speed over ground, and control status.

Listing 1. Templates of the `ship0` and environment facts `leeway` representing vessel state and interval estimates of leeway conditions

```
ship0(IDs,Dimensions,Timestamp,(X,Y),COG,SOG,Under_ctrl)
leeway(IDl,Cornerpoints,DirectionInterval,SpeedInterval)
```

whereas, a close-quarter situation between two ships can be described as in Listing 2:

Listing 2. Rule to detect a critical approach between two vessels

```
critical_approach(IDi,IDj):-
ship(IDi,Dimensions_i,Timestamp_i,Position_i,COG_i,SOG_i,
Under_ctrl_i),
ship(IDj,Dimensions_j,Timestamp_j,Position_j,COG_j,SOG_j,
Under_ctrl_j),
critical_distance(Position_i,Position_j).
```

This rule states that a critical approach occurs if the `critical_distance` predicate holds between two ships, each defined by a rule as the one shown in Listing 1.

These data points serve as input for both static rule evaluation and dynamic simulation.

A proxy server is implemented to automatically retrieve and cache sea mark data (S-57 format) from the Norwegian Mapping Authority (NMA), enriching the knowledge base with real-world navigational references. The front-end user interface is developed as a web application, providing an interactive and browser-based platform for scenario creation and result visualization. Data persistence and spatial layers are managed using a PostgreSQL database. A lightweight Flask back-end handles routing, business logic, and communication between the interface and the Prolog solver, while a Python-implemented middleware bridges JSON data structures between the components.

VSF is implemented also as a Flask server and it provides a RESTful API agnostic to the simulation technology used. It also allows to run simulations faster than real-time depending of the configuration of the models used. Telemetry and event logs are collected into a structured simulation report, which supports both interactive review and batch analysis. Figure 4 illustrates how navigation data is interactively managed through the graphical user interface. Polygons in orange denote convex hull of non-navigable zones.

VI. EVALUATION

To validate the proposed approach, we employ a representative case study using the co-simulation model of a Dynamic Positioning (DP) system, hereafter referred to as the DP-ship [10]. The model (see Figure 5) simulates a vessel equipped with an offshore DP system that automatically maintains its position and heading using onboard propellers and thrusters. The DP-ship dynamics and open sea conditions are co-simulated using in VSF using the Open Simulation Platform (OSP) [11], a simulation framework widely adopted in the maritime industry. OSP supports modular integration, co-simulation and testing of simulation components from multiple stakeholders using standardized interfaces based on the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) [12].

Fig. 4. GUI Component for Data Extraction in the VSF.

By integrating our path planning framework with the DP-ship environment, we evaluated the system's performance under realistic marine conditions, including its response to external disturbances and its ability to follow COLREG-compliant paths. Within this setup, the *Reference Generator* module receives the planned by CVT vessel path as waypoint coordinates and generates a continuous *reference path* for the *DP Controller*. The latter is in charge of adjusting the vessel position based on its current position as reported by the *Observer* and the reference coordinates. The vessel is actuated by the *Thrust Allocation* which communicates to the *Ship* module the thrust force, torque, and angles used by the two azimuth thrusters placed symmetrical at the stern and the one tunnel thruster in the bow. The Vessel model also includes an irregular sea-state, currents, and simple hydrodynamics.

Fig. 5. DP-Ship Case Study.

In the case study, it was observed that the ship controller tends to overshoot the reference path and subsequently compensates by undershooting, before eventually stabilizing on the correct path (see for example Figure 6). This overshooting behavior can lead to grounding incidents if not properly managed. By systematically varying the path planning parameters, several anomalous cases were uncovered, highlighting the sensitivity of the system to parameter settings and emphasizing the need for careful tuning. However, these cases were avoided with the help of CVT by applying real-time corrections to the planned trajectories, while maintaining of fuel-efficiency of the path, thus showing the feasibility of our approach.

Fig. 6. Reference (blue) vs actual (green) path example.

VII. SCALABILITY ANALYSIS

In our approach, the Explorer component is responsible for the exploration and reduction of the constraint space, as illustrated in Figure 7. In the 3D plot, the x-axis represents the heading of ship A, the y-axis represents the heading of ship B, and the z-axis shows the corresponding average reduction rate. This visualization highlights which heading pairs most effectively reduce the search space for potential collision detection. The reduction rate represents the average decrease computed for all positions of ship A, assessed against various positions of ship B, with both ships maintaining fixed courses.

As shown in our previous work [13] geometric optimization can predict positions that are likely to lead to a collision. Given the starting position and heading of the first ship, the set of initial positions of the second ship, assuming its heading is known, that can lead to a potential collision (CQS) forms a segment. Darker blue regions indicate longer segments, corresponding to a greater number of initial positions that may lead to collisions. In contrast, lighter yellow regions represent shorter segments, indicating fewer initial positions likely to result in collisions. Additionally, the yellow spikes correspond to null segments, indicating that no initial position leads to a collision under the given conditions. We notice that we can reduce the search space by up to 90%. Using this insight, we generate a set of waypoints that start with critical initial positions, those with a high likelihood of collision. This approach significantly reduces the time required to verify whether ships comply with COLREGs and ensures that they are able to avoid collisions.

In addition to reducing the number of initial positions, we discretize the value domains of ship positions, speeds, navigation conditions, and all other system parameters to be verified by specifying a fixed granularity. This discretization yields finite value sets, which significantly reduces the verification time. Although a coarser granularity enables faster exploration, it can degrade the quality of the verification by overlooking fine-grained scenarios. Allowing the simulator to adjust values within this coarse granularity facilitates the search for an optimal trade-off between verification accuracy and computational efficiency. This makes the DP-Ship case study more than just a benchmark for performance; it also serves as a crucial diagnostic tool, allowing the system to be

thoroughly tested and validated before being used in real-world scenarios.

Fig. 7. Reduction rate distribution.

VIII. DISCUSSION

The proposed approach demonstrates promising potential across several practical applications. The generated COLREG-compliant paths, refined with dynamic constraints, can be employed for verification purposes in virtual harbor acceptance testing and during real-world sea trials. Additionally, the path planning solutions offer valuable support for assisted steering systems. Beyond operational deployment, the generated paths can be utilized in pilot training through scenario-based simulation games and serve as synthetic datasets for training machine learning models in maritime navigation. Despite these strengths, the current solution has certain limitations. Notably, it does not yet incorporate probabilistic constraints, which could enhance the robustness of decision-making under uncertainty. Furthermore, the scalability of the approach requires further validation; performance testing on larger scenarios—specifically involving more than ten vessels and multiple obstacles concurrently—is necessary to establish more reliable benchmarks for practical deployment.

This incremental refinement approach allows us to effectively tackle an otherwise NP-complete problem in a computationally feasible manner.

IX. FUTURE WORK

Future work will focus on extending the CVT-VSF framework with stochastic capabilities, allowing for the estimation and modeling of path disturbances and data imprecision directly within the path planning process. Incorporating such uncertainty-aware mechanisms will enable the system to account for external disturbances—such as wind, waves, and sensor inaccuracies—resulting in more robust and risk-sensitive paths. Another important direction is the integration of external data sources for automatic model updates. Real-time vessel data from platforms such as www.myshiptracking.com can be used to dynamically update traffic patterns and vessel behavior models, while environmental data from tools like the NOAA Office for Coastal Management’s Sea Level Rise

Viewer can provide critical insights into changing coastal conditions, aiding in the adaptation of navigational safety margins. In addition, the CVT-VSF framework is planned to be ported to the AI-Captain stack of MindChip’s commercial M-series MASSs. This will involve adapting the current implementation for compatibility with the AI-Captain’s planning interface and middleware, enabling real-time integration with sensor data and autonomous control systems. Collectively, these developments aim to enhance the scalability, adaptability, and operational readiness of the proposed planning approach in real-world maritime environments.

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